
NASA Lunabotics: Drivetrain

Elicitation Report
02/27/2025

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1. Purpose

The purpose of this document is to provide a structured and organized report of a requirement elicitation process. This report analyses Team Statement and NASA's Rules. The intentions behind this document are to capture essential information obtained during the analysis, document any findings, and outline action items and next steps based on the team's responses.

1.1 Project Overview

NASA Lunabotics is a competition that challenges teams of university students to design, build, and operate a robotic system in moon-like environment. The teams are tasked to have a robot that is able to navigate through the arena from the starting zone down to the mining zone, mine regolith-simulant, and build a berm in a designated construction zone.

The focus of this document will be the Drivetrain subsystem of the robot that the ERAU's team will be designing for the competition. The drivetrain will be a wheel-based design with a steering mechanism(s) to ensure efficient movement.

1.2 References

NASA. *Lunabotics 2025 Guidebook*. NASA, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nasa.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/lunaboticsguidebook-2025.pdf>

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2. NASA Guidebook

This section contains a condensed version of the guidebook provided by NASA for the competition. Since only the drivetrain is being analyzed, only relevant requirements will be shown. Appendix A will contain all of the rules.

2.1 Relevant Rules

2. Robot Requirements

1. Volumetric dimensions - robot(s) shall be contained within a payload envelope measuring 1.50 m length x 0.75 m width x 0.75 m height. The orientation of these dimensions may be chosen by the team. It may deploy or expand beyond the envelope after the start of each attempt but shall not exceed 1.75 m in additional height (which is 2.5 m above the surface of the regolith). Multiple robot systems are allowed but the starting dimensions of the whole system (all the robots) shall comply with the volumetric dimensions given in this rule.
2. Robots will be inspected for the volumetric dimensions in the stowed configuration during the Safety Inspection. A "jig" frame will be placed over the rover for volume constraint verification. No modifications or team robot interaction is permitted during this verification.
 - Robot Mass - a maximum mass of 80kg. Subsystems/equipment on the robot that are used to transmit commands / data and video to the telerobotic operators are counted toward the mass limit.
7. The robot can run either by telerobotic (remote control) or in autonomous operations and cannot have any touch sensors to sense and avoid obstacles.

4. Power Meters / Data Loggers

1. The robot shall provide its own onboard power. No facility power will be provided to the robot during the attempt. There are no power limitations except that the robot must be self-powered and included in the maximum mass limit. Shall be schematically located between the battery and kill switch, so the readings are not erased if the E-STOP button is activated. The devices shall be placed on the highest practical location on the robot and be easily visible.

5. Battery Protocol

12. Teams may not use GPS, rubber pneumatic tires; air/foam filled tires; open or closed cell foam, ultrasonic proximity sensors; or hydraulics because NASA does not anticipate the use of these on an off-world mission. This will not pass inspection,

6. Robotic Operations

4. The robot may not use any process that causes the physical or chemical properties of the regolith simulant to be changed or otherwise endangers the uniformity between competition attempts. The mining robot may not penetrate the regolith simulant surface with more force than the weight of the mining robot before the start of each competition attempt.
5. No ordnance, projectile, far-reaching mechanism, etc. may be used. The mining robot must move on the regolith simulant surface.

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3. Team Statement

This section contains a sample statement from the ERAU’s Team, the customer. The statement consists of constraints from set design choices, goals of the team, and manufacturability constraints. The numbers at the end of some sentences will be used to easier reference customer requirements.

3.1 Statement

Project Description

The Embry-Riddle team wants to design a robotic system that will achieve the goals of the competition. The team has looked at last year’s system and identified what concepts and designs are to be preserved and what needs to be changed. The team also lists objectives that are to be pursued and may affect all subsystems.

The focus of this document will be on the Drivetrain Subassembly.

Project Technical Objectives

The project technical objectives are goals that drive the design of the system and the creation of key requirements:

1. Maximize Automation
 - a. The robot shall be capable of performing a “Full Autonomy” competition run as specified in the Lunabotics 2025 Guidebook. All subsystems shall have the required sensors and functions to complete this goal. ¹
2. Minimize Mass/Maximize Mass-to-Payload Ratio
 - a. The robot should have a low total mass and have a high mass-to-payload ratio. ²
3. Minimize Energy Consumption
 - a. The robot should be energy efficient when performing functions including navigation, excavation, and construction. ³
4. Maximize Dust Protection
 - a. The robot should have enough dust protection features that dust will not have a negative effect on the robot throughout a long operation time. ⁴
5. Maximize Operational Flexibility
 - a. The robot should be capable of constructing berms of different shapes and sizes. The robot should be able to execute multiple strategies for excavating regolith. ⁵

Functionality

- The robot shall be able to go up to 0.6 m/s ⁶
- The robot shall be capable of performing a 180 degrees “zero-point” turn. ⁷

Physical

- The robot shall be contained within a payload envelope measuring 1.50 m x 0.75 m x 0.75 m in the initial starting configuration. ⁸
- The robot’s initial mass shall not exceed 40kg. ⁹
- The target payload that the robot shall transport is 35kg. ¹⁰
- The drivetrain’s mass shall not exceed 12.5 kg. ¹¹
- The robot shall have an Ingress Protection (IP) rating of IP6X or greater. ¹²

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Autonomy

- The robot shall be able to fulfill all functional requirements without direct input from mission control center.¹³
- The robot shall execute machine control commands autonomously.¹⁴
- The robot shall not execute machine control commands from the mission control center while operating autonomously.¹⁵
- The robot shall end autonomous operation if instructed to do so by mission control center.¹⁶
- The robot shall not begin autonomous operations until instructed to do so by the mission control center.¹⁷
- The navigation system shall be able to localize the robot within the competition arena.¹⁸
- The robot shall regularly send telemetry data to the mission control center.¹⁹

Power:

- The robot shall measure the power drawn by all major components.²⁰
- The power system shall utilize Flex 24v batteries to power the robot.²¹
- The drivetrain shall not expend more than 18 Wh of energy in a single competition run.²²

Constraints/Old Design Choices:

The old excavation method will be used. A front loader bucket is used; all the payload mass will be there, and it will stretch no more than 50 cm in front of the front of the robot. The front two wheels shall be able to withstand stresses associated; assume the center of mass is close to the front wheels.²³

The old wheel design had grousers that aided in traction in regolith; the drivetrain’s wheels shall contain grousers.²⁴ The team also aims to optimize the size and spacing of grousers to maximize traction.²⁵

Manufacturing Constraints:

The chassis shall be made of 1in x 1in aluminum square tubes; the drivetrain shall be installed on the tubes.²⁶ The drivetrain shall be fastened using reusable methods to make the drivetrain easier to maintain.²⁷ The fasteners shall withstand the vibrations exerted by the drivetrain.²⁸

The team will 3D print the wheels out of PETG.²⁹ Due to the size of printers available, the maximum diameter of the wheel, grouser to grouser, is 28 cm.³⁰

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4. Action Items

4.1 Inconsistencies

Below is a list of inconsistent items found during the review of NASA's Guidelines and Team Statement:

- The robot mass in statement number 9 does not match NASA's rule 2.2.: 40kg versus 80kg

4.2 Unclear Items

Below is a list of items that require clarification after a review of NASA's Guidelines and Team Statement:

- What is meant by "Zero-point" turn? How is turning/steering expected to be handled? (Statement 7)
- What would quantify as "regular" when it comes to sending telemetry? (Statement 19)
- Is the telemetry sent during the whole run or just under autonomous operations? (Statement 19)
- How much stress are back wheels are expected to handle, or would they simply be identical to the front wheels? (Statement 23)
- Is the system expected to switch back to autonomous operations once they have been ended? (Statement 16)
- How should the drivetrain behave if the commands stop coming in?

4.3 Questions and Answers

Below is a list of questions that came about after the analysis of NASA's Guidelines and Team Statement and the answers from the team:

1. NASA's Guidelines state that the max robot mass is 80kg but the Team Statement provided said it is 40kg, can you clarify?
 - a. While NASA allows up to 80kg, you score better if your mass is lower. That is why the team is aiming for 40kg.
2. What is meant by "Zero-point" turn?
 - a. The robot should be able to turn on the spot; the team wants the robot to stop moving forward/backwards and change its heading without of changing its location.
3. How is turning/steering expected to be handled?
 - a. Currently the robot has the capability to do that using differential steering, which simply uses the motors that run the wheels forward/backwards. While the team wants to maintain that option as a backup during the competition, the team also would like the drivetrain to have the ability to switch to and from swerve steering. That is when the wheels are angled in a way that minimizes skidding across the surface. Having that control over wheel direction, over the rotation of the robot if you will, be separated from the regular motors would be preferable.
4. What would quantify as "regular" when it comes to sending telemetry? (Statement 19)
 - a. No more than half a second.
5. Is the telemetry sent during the whole run or just under autonomous operations?
 - a. Whole run, the team want to collect the data in case things go wrong.
6. How much stress are back wheels are expected to handle, or would they simply be identical to the front wheels?
 - a. For simplicity of manufacturing, all 4 wheels will be the same. We plan on printing more wheels as extras, so having them all be the same is beneficial there too.

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4.4 Further Inquiries

Below are any inquiries that came throughout Requirements Analysis step of the process, primarily when creating different models.

7. How should the drivetrain behave if the commands stop coming in?
 - a. If there are no new commands coming for half a second or more, regardless of what mode the robot is in, all actuators must be stopped.

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Appendix A: Full NASA Rules

The verbatim transcript consists of the full dialogue between Dr. Bryan Watson and the five teams of requirement engineers conducting the elicitation interview. Dr. Watson’s dialogue is labeled, as is Dr. Omar Ochoa’s. The interviewers conducting are labeled collectively by team name.

ROBOTS AND ROBOTIC OPERATIONS

1. Robots

1. Lunar bulk regolith construction requires teams to consider several design and operation factors such as high robot dust tolerance and minimizing dust projection, efficient communications, minimizing vehicle mass, minimizing energy/power required, and maximizing autonomy. Each team will have the opportunity to complete two construction competition runs to demonstrate their design.
2. Students on the team shall perform 100% of this project (including design, construction, and task components of their vehicle and deliverables, and including performing or supervising work that is supported by a professional machinist for the purpose of training or safety). Components (i.e. electronic, mechanical, etc.) are not required to be space qualified for atmospheric, electromagnetic, thermal, or Lunar environments.

2. Robot Requirements

1. Volumetric dimensions - robot(s) shall be contained within a payload envelope measuring 1.50 m length x 0.75 m width x 0.75 m height. The orientation of these dimensions may be chosen by the team. It may deploy or expand beyond the envelop after the start of each attempt but shall not exceed 1.75 m in additional height (which is 2.5 m above the surface of the regolith). Multiple robot systems are allowed but the starting dimensions of the whole system (all the robots) shall comply with the volumetric dimensions given in this rule.
2. Robots will be inspected for the volumetric dimensions in the stowed configuration during the Safety Inspection. A “jig” frame will be placed over the rover for volume constraint verification. No modifications or team robot interaction is permitted during this verification.
 - Robot Mass - a maximum mass of 80kg. Subsystems/equipment on the robot that are used to transmit commands / data and video to the telerobotic operators are counted toward the mass limit.
 - The mass of the navigational aid system, including any beacons or targets not attached to the robot, is included in the maximum mining robot mass limit of and must be self-powered.
3. Equipment not on the robot used to receive data from and send commands to the robot for telerobotic operations is excluded from the mass limit. Multiple robot systems are allowed but the total mass of the whole system shall comply with the mass given in this rule. The commercial cost of delivering payloads to the Moon is about \$1.2 Million per kg (estimate). This competition aims to simulate a Lunar mission where a robot is delivered to the Moon. This corresponds to an approximate mission cost of \$72 Million. Lower masses will result in lower mission costs so this competition rewards teams that have a lower robot mass.
4. External robot antennas are required to reduce potential interference problems.
5. Robots shall have a minimum of four (4) lifting points, safe for human hands and clearly marked (ISO 7000-1368) for students and staff to use. Teams are responsible for placement and removal of their construction robot onto the BP-1 surface. There must be one person per 20 kg of mass of the construction robot, requiring a minimum of four people to carry the maximum allowed mass of 80 kg.
6. The robot can separate itself intentionally, if desired, but all parts of the robot must be under the team’s control at all times. Unintentional breakage will not be counted against the team. The robot does not have to re-assemble prior to the end of the competition run.
7. The robot can run either by telerobotic (remote control) or in autonomous operations and cannot have any touch sensors to sense and avoid obstacles.
8. Reference Points / Reference Arrows - The launch volume dimensions of the robot may be oriented in any way (length, width, height can be defined along any of the X, Y, Z axes, dimensions correspond to the typical payload volume available on today’s Lunar landers).
 - The team must declare the robot orientation by length (arrow 1) and width (arrow 2) to the inspection judge. Reference Point (arrow 3) - must mark the forward direction of the mining robot in the starting position configuration (the reference location and arrow pointing forward can point any direction of the team’s choosing, except up or down). The arrow is used only to orientate the robot prior to starting the robot run to face the robot arrow either north, east, south, or west after spinning the direction wheel.
 - The judges will use this reference point and arrow to orient the mining robot in the randomly selected direction and position (you can use a permanent-type marker) indicating the team’s choice of forward direction on any location on the robot is acceptable if multiple arrows do not conflict.

3. E-STOP Button

1. Also known more formally as an emergency brake, emergency stop (E-stop), emergency off (EMO), kill switch, or emergency power off (EPO), is a safety mechanism used to shut off machinery in an emergency, when it cannot be shut down in the usual manner.
2. OSHA and relevant standards such as IEC 60204-1 state that an e-stop must be readily accessible to the operator.

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Additionally, it should be unobstructed—no collars or actuation restrictions—and easily accessible without having to reach over, under or around to actuate. Machine-building standards such as ANSI B11, B11-19 and National Fire Protection Agency (NFPA) 79 also address specifics in regard to safety devices such as an e-stop.

3. OSHA and relevant standards such as IEC 60204-1 further state that resetting of the e-stop alone shall not resume operation. A second deliberate action is needed, such as the pressing of a reset button. This could include twisting the mushroom button and allowing it to spring back up or pulling the button back up to reset. It cannot automatically reset.
4. The robot shall be equipped with an E-STOP button. An unmodified “Commercial Off-The-Shelf” (COTS) red button is required. Use sound engineering practices and principles in placing and securing the E-STOP button on your robot(s), failure to do so may result in a safety disqualification. The E-STOP button shall have a minimum diameter of 40 mm and require no additional steps to access it.
5. The E-STOP button shall be placed on the highest practical location on the robot. There shall be only one E-STOP button per robot and in the case of multiple robots, each robot shall have its own E-STOP button
6. Disabling the E-STOP button without authorization from the Staff shall result in a safety disqualification.
7. The E-STOP button shall stop the construction robot’s motion and disable power with one push motion on the button. It shall be reliable and instantaneous. A closed control signal to a mechanical relay is allowed as long as it stays open to disable the robot. This rule exists in order to have the capability to safe the construction robot in the event of a fire or other mishap. The button shall disconnect the batteries from all controllers (high current, forklift type button) and it shall isolate the batteries from the rest of the active sub-systems as well.
8. Only onboard laptop computers may stay powered on if powered by its own, independent, internal computer battery. For example: it is acceptable to have a small battery onboard that only powers a Raspberry Pi control computer, and whose power does not flow through the main robot E-STOP button.

4. Power Meters / Data Loggers

1. The robot shall provide its own onboard power. No facility power will be provided to the robot during the attempt. There are no power limitations except that the robot must be self-powered and included in the maximum mass limit. Shall be schematically located between the battery and kill switch, so the readings are not erased if the E-STOP button is activated. The devices shall be placed on the highest practical location on the robot and be easily visible.
2. The energy consumed shall be recorded with a “Commercial Off-The-Shelf” (COTS) electronic data logger device. Actual energy consumed during each attempt shall be shown to the judges on the data logger immediately after the attempt (‘immediate’ includes time for the judge climbing into the arena, finding the logger, and recording the power reading). If the logger is independently powered, then the robot can be remotely powered off after the run. Although this is acceptable, it is not recommended in case the robot needs to be commanded to complete an operation so that it can be removed from the arena.

5. Battery Protocol

1. This for the Lithium-Ion / Nic-Cad batteries used in your robots.
2. Batteries must be attended while charging. Chargers shall be unplugged overnight.
3. Battery containers must be designed for safely storing, charging, and transporting lithium-ion batteries, or approved equivalent.
4. Batteries must be stored in upright containers; batteries cannot be in contact with each other.
5. Batteries that have been dropped must be inspected for damage and replaced as needed.
6. Do not store batteries that are hot to the touch after charging.
7. If a battery continues to feel hot after charging, if possible, remove from the building and place outside and notify NASA Fire as a non-emergency issue.
8. No one will fault you if in your opinion you need to call NASA Fire at 321.867.7911.
9. To ensure the robot is usable for an actual mission, it cannot employ any fundamental physical processes, gases, fluids, or consumables that would not work in an off-world environment. For example, any dust removal from a lens or sensor must employ a physical process that would be suitable for the Lunar surface. Teams may use processes that require an Earth-like environment (e.g., oxygen, water) only if the system using the processes is designed to work in a Lunar environment and if such resources used by the robot are included in the mass of the robot. Closed pneumatic systems are allowed if the gas is supplied by the robot itself. Pneumatic systems are permitted if the gas is supplied by the robot and self-contained.
10. The rules are intended for robots to show an off-world plausible system functionality, but the components do not have to be traceable to an off-world qualified component version. Examples of allowable components are: Sealed Lead-Acid (SLA) or Nickel Metal Hydride (NiMH) batteries; composite materials; rubber or plastic parts; actively fan cooled electronics; motors with brushes; infrared sensors, inertial measurement units, and proximity detectors

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and/or Hall Effect sensors, but proceed at your own risk since LHS-1 & BP-1 regolith simulant is very dusty and abrasive

11. Teams may use honeycomb structures as long as they are strong enough to be safe and the edges sealed to prevent dust intrusion, a wheel with a large honeycomb structures that is open on both sides is allowed as long as the edges are not so sharp that they would be a cutting hazard.
12. Teams may not use GPS, rubber pneumatic tires; air/foam filled tires; open or closed cell foam, ultrasonic proximity sensors; or hydraulics because NASA does not anticipate the use of these on an off-world mission. This will not pass inspection,

6. Robotic Operations

1. The robot cannot be anchored to the sand prior to the beginning of the proof of life demonstration.
2. At the start of the competition run, the mining robot may not occupy any location outside the defined starting position in the regolith arena.
3. The robot must operate within the regolith arena; it is not permitted to pass beyond the confines of the outside perimeter of the arena or hit the walls during the competition run.
4. The robot may not use any process that causes the physical or chemical properties of the regolith simulant to be changed or otherwise endangers the uniformity between competition attempts. The mining robot may not penetrate the regolith simulant surface with more force than the weight of the mining robot before the start of each competition attempt.
5. No ordnance, projectile, far-reaching mechanism, etc. may be used. The mining robot must move on the regolith simulant surface.
6. Far-reaching mechanism in this context does not include any deployed or extended component as allowed in the dimensions rule above, those will not violate this rule.
7. Beacons or fiducial targets may be attached to the designated arena frame area for navigation purposes only. The designated area is anywhere on the bin frame structure along the perimeter of the starting zone (2 sides). Tape, clamps, or rods pushed into the regolith may be used, but screws or other fasteners requiring holes may not be used. This navigational aid system must be attached during the setup time and removed afterwards during the removal time.
8. The beacon may send a signal or light beam or use a laser-based detection system which have not been modified (optics or power). Only Class I or Class II laser or low powered lasers (< 5mW) are allowed. Supporting documentation from the laser instrumentation vendor must be provided to the responsible faculty member for "eye-safe" lasers.

*Figure 1: Beacon Mounting locations
(note: the ducts along the sides of the Arena walls are 17cm diameter).*

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